

Cross-species Standardised Subcortical Tractography

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Introduction: White matter (WM) bundles connecting cortical areas with subcortical nuclei are crucial for relaying and modulating cortical function (1,2). Their disruption is linked to abnormal function and pathology in neurodegenerative and mental health disorders (3,4). Diffusion MRI (dMRI) and tractography enable exploration and reconstruction of WM bundles (5,6), but their relative size, the complexity and associated bottlenecks, make their estimation challenging and sensitive to anatomical priors (7,8). Standardised tractography approaches (9,10) provide a way to overcome these challenges enabling reproducible and consistent bundle delineation. Previous efforts involved cortico-cortical connecting bundles, or tract reconstruction using subject-specific protocols (11). Here we build upon our previous work (9,12,13) introducing tractography protocols for delineating cortico-subcortical connections, between cortex and the amygdala, hippocampus, striatum and thalamus. Guided by chemical tracer literature in the macaque, we devised protocols for the macaque, and then extended to the human. We incorporated these protocols into a common space framework (13,14) and assessed their efficacy in predicting subcortical nuclei across species based on their connectivity patterns.

Methods: Tractography protocols for 7 subcortical bundles were defined using a standardised approach (9). They were first defined for the macaque brain and then transferred to the human using correspondingly defined landmarks. Each protocol included a unique combination of anatomically-defined masks, delineated in standard macaque space (F99), chosen based on literature descriptions of the tracts (eg. macaque tract-tracer studies). Protocols included the amygdalofugal tract (AMF), anterior commissure, sensorimotor and frontal cortico-striatal bundle (STB) / extreme capsule (EC), sensorimotor and frontal Muratoff Bundle (MB)/Subcallosal Fasciculus. Even if not a cortico-subcortical bundle, we included the extreme capsule (EmC) that runs close to the putamen connecting the insula and frontal cortices.

These protocols were added to our standardised set of cross-species XTRACT protocols of mainly cortico-cortical bundles (9,12). Using dMRI data from 6 ex-vivo rhesus macaque brains (13) (available through PRIME-DE) and 50 unrelated HCP subjects (15) we performed tractography in human and macaque. We evaluated the new protocols in 2 ways. First, we assessed if the addition of subcortical bundles allowed identification of cross-species similarities of subcortical nuclei, based on their connectivity patterns to respective landmark

Figure 1 Tractography and tracer results. MB: Muratoff bundle/Subcallosal fasciculus; StB/EC: Striatal bundle/external capsule; EmC: extreme capsule. Tracer image adapted from Schmahmann & Pandya, 2009.

bundles. KL-divergence was used as a measure of divergence as in (13,14). Then, we explored if including subcortical tracts increases predictability of cortical areas and translation of cortical maps across species. We used measured T1/T2 (myelin) maps for human and macaques and assessed if subcortical connections improve predictability of one from the other (12,13).

Results/Discussion: Fig.1 shows examples of tractography reconstructions relative to bundles identified by chemical tracing, and how their relative positions are preserved across macaques and humans (e.g. EmC is more lateral than the EC, MB is at the dorsal tip of the caudate). Fig.2 shows maximum intensity projections of the reconstructed tracts. Using the similarity of connectivity patterns of subcortical nuclei to WM tracts, we identified corresponding nuclei between humans and macaques (Fig.3) when considering subcortical tracts (blue dashed line, Fig.3A), compared to not using them (red dashed line). For instance, human putamen has more similar connectivity (lower divergence) to macaque putamen, with STBs contributing to their connectivity profile, compared e.g. to macaque hippocampus or thalamus that connect to other bundles. Similarly, we used the cross-species similarity of connectivity patterns throughout the cortex to translate cortical myelin maps. Our myelin map prediction was improved in both species when considering subcortical tracts (Fig. 4, $r=0.8$ vs 0.74).

Figure 2. Maximum intensity projections of the new subcortical bundles for macaques and humans. Averages of 6 animals and 50 human subjects.

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Figure 3. KL divergence between corresponding human and macaque subcortical ROIs. (A) KL-Divergence values of macaque to human subcortical nuclei, when new subcortical tracts are included (blue dashed line) vs not (red dashed line). (B) KLD maps in the macaque for human nuclei (each row for a different human nucleus – left hemisphere).

Figure 4. Predicted macaque myelin maps from human ones, based on similarity of connectivity patterns to WM tracts. Prediction is better with the addition of subcortical tracts.

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